

Stiffness Changes in an Orthotropic Lamina under Fatigue

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work is to characterize fatigue damage in a general anisotropic laminate in terms of changes in its stiffness properties. The first step towards this objective is to examine stiffness changes in an orthotropic lamina subjected to fatigue loading along a principal axis.

In a recent work by the author [1], a procedure for measuring changes in the four independent elastic constants of an orthotropic lamina, which was subjected to fatigue, was presented. The novel feature of this work was a specimen design that allowed fatigue loading and the measurement of all the elastic constants on the same specimen. The procedure used three loading modes, namely, longitudinal tension, off-axis tension and transverse compression for the measurement of elastic constants. The strains were measured by rosette gauges placed symmetrically on both faces of the specimen. The elastic constants measured were the longitudinal E - modulus, the inplane shear modulus and the major and the minor Poisson's ratios. The feasibility of the procedure was demonstrated.

The present work uses the procedure proposed in [1] to examine the stiffness changes in a unidirectional glass/polyester composite subjected to tensile fatigue in the fibre direction. The stiffness changes are measured following different number of cycles applied at various strain amplitudes. From the measured stiffness changes inferences can be made regarding the underlying fatigue damage mechanisms. For instance, at low amplitudes, where matrix microcracking may be the operative mechanism, no significant change in the E - modulus in the fibre direction is seen. The transverse E - modulus, as calculated from the two measured Poisson's ratios, shows some change. As the applied load amplitudes increase, the fibre damage and the consequent interfacial damage are reflected in the changes in the E - modulus and the G - modulus. A steady state in some stiffness property is seen while other properties continue to change with the number of cycles applied. Fig. 1 shows one example of such behaviour.

The effect of volume fraction of fibres on stiffness changes in fatigue of unidirectional composites is also examined.

The investigation reported here is part of a continuing effort to develop

procedures for life prediction and non-destructive inspection of multi-directional laminates based on stiffness property changes.

Reference

[1] Talreja, R., "Stiffness based fatigue damage characterization of fibrous composites", Advances in Composite Materials, Ed. by A.R. Bunsell, et al., Pergamon Press, Proc. of ICCM 3, Paris, 26-29 Aug. 1980, Vol. 2, pp.1732-1737, 1980.

Fig. 1. Variation of the normalized elastic constants with the number of cycles applied.